

When Comparing the United States and Vietnam, What Factors Appear to Contribute the Most to Incidences and Prosecution of Human Trafficking?

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ABSTRACT:

This research explores many components that seem to be driving forces of what causes human trafficking to be more severe in Vietnam than in the United States. Majority of nations have demonstrated their efforts by enacting their own versions of laws with the intentions of eliminating trafficking. Although already established laws in each country punish individuals for the same offenses, they are not all equally effective. In this report, I compare the laws surrounding human trafficking in Vietnam and the United States as well as the effectiveness of their enforcement through the use of personal anecdotes as well as research. It demonstrates how compared to America, Vietnam exhibits more corruption in their general anti-trafficking policies and in the overall government. In addition to the government, a nation's physical characteristics influence how widespread human trafficking is. Considering how, in comparison to the geography of America, Vietnam's topography and terrain enable human trafficking in Asia.

Keywords: Human trafficking, Vietnam, Enforcements, Societal Impacts, Geography

1. I. INTRODUCTION

Living in Vietnam during the time period of 1954 to 1975 during the Vietnam war, people's lives became controlled by the government. The government dictated what citizens were allowed to do on their land such as agricultural activities and construction, and the government exercised arbitrary power to limit the boundaries of the land. "Land Regulations". Additionally, they filtered online content and blocked websites; on certain occasions, they also removed blogs, imposed fines, and suspended websites that opposed government policies. As a result, it soon became difficult for people to predict whether their homes would stand for another day or would it be destroyed in between the attacks from the North and the South. While many people died in war, many others fled, preferring to die in the ocean over their homeland, which was being taken over by North Vietnam ("The Boat's People Journey"). Instead of staying and falling victim to sexual trafficking by soldiers, many women also adopted dangerous methods of fleeing.

Desperately looking for an alternative, the Vietnamese migrated to any land they could find access to, that would take them in. Upon arrival, they had to fight hunger, harsh weather, cramped and dirty ships, and the occasional pirates along the way ("Seeking asylum: Facing pirates, storms and gunfire to flee Vietnam," 2019). Hanh Tran in her book (?) "Seeking asylum:

Facing pirates, storms and gunfire to flee Vietnam,” documented her story of escaping Vietnam. She stated,

“My mom told me a story of how her aunt fled Vietnam during the war. She was hoping to land in any country possible but strove for America. My mom’s aunt described her reckless journey to an asylum in Hong Kong as she waits to enter the United States. She briefly mentioned the few drops of water she got on the boat each day and the stench from everyone in the packed ships. More specifically, she talked about how pirates were roaming the sea and the things that they’d do to a refugee ship” (Phan, 2020).

A UPI Archives article reported in 1981, that women were often captured and raped repeatedly, then thrown overboard to drown. Eighty percent of refugee boats that arrived in Thailand reported encountering pirates, of which 540 women reported being raped by pirates (“Pirates rape women,” 1981).

Pirates would typically hunt down the ships and raid the boats for people’s money or anything of value. Phan (2020) narrated stories where his mother recalled how her aunt saw women being sexually assaulted by men with black cloths over their faces. She added that women often put dirt on their face and cut off their hair in order to look as ugly as possible to escape their capture (Phan, 2020). Women who were forced off the boats by the pirates had only one ending: sex trafficking and being left to die. They would often be sexually abused and then possibly sold off to prostitution or the sex entertainment industry in return for more money. This is what many people risked to do when escaping Vietnam. Through means of getting to America, women often risked their life and took journeys where their lives would turn into a life worse than before they migrated.

This was a dangerous journey from start to finish where many people were vulnerable to human trafficking. There are, however, many more stories and experiences of human trafficking that were not derived from war: they usually started off like an opportunity for the victim but soon turned into a fraud. The global issue of human trafficking has prompted many nations to initiate their own campaigns such as the Blue Campaign, against modern slavery through government-supported organization and the enforcement of laws. The trafficking of people is their recruitment for the purpose of personal gains through the use of coercion, fraud, or deception (“What is Human Trafficking”). This commonly accepted international concept or definition formed by the United Nations allows for the justification of factors which together outline why human trafficking is illegal in many countries and why it aligns closely with the definition, all aiming to combat human trafficking.

For example, in the United States the three elements proving someone is guilty of human trafficking are: (1) anyone who recruits, harbors, transports, provides, or obtains a person (2) through the means of force, fraud, or coercion (3) with the intent of obtaining commercial sex or to exploit the individual for labor or services; with a penalty of up to 20 years in prison (“Federal Crime of Human Trafficking”). Along with the United States, over 175 nations in the world have legislation in place to prevent human trafficking (“About Human Trafficking”).

Vietnam also follows the international definition of human trafficking in order to penalize people for the act of trafficking with a fine of \$800 to \$2000 in addition to five to ten years of prison (“2023 Trafficking in Persons Report: Vietnam”). Vietnam and the United States go by very similar laws with the difference being the penalty in each country. This may lead many to wonder why the same laws have led to huge differences in human trafficking volumes in each country especially when it’s even more severe in Asia. Human trafficking not only depends on the ratification of a law but also other factors including a country’s economy and/or how the laws are enforced. Vietnam does worse economically and also politically in enforcing their laws when compared to the United States. Vietnam also suffers from the effects of the geography it lies in and peoples’ decisions who live in more harsh areas become more impacted. This explains why the United States may be seeing more improvement than Vietnam. These factors, though, still do not prevent trafficking all the way and its cases still persist in this world to this day.

ii. Legal Definition of Human Trafficking

There are three elements which make human trafficking a very detailed crime and have specific examples which could be used to prove whether someone is involved in human trafficking. The first element consists of ‘anyone who recruits, harbors, transports, provides, or obtains a person’—could be elaborated and broken down even more. When someone first reads this, they might envision someone getting swooped up forcefully by someone into a vehicle and driven away. This could be the case, but the definition also includes “harbor” and “recruits” in cases where someone is isolated or targeted for their vulnerability. In simple terms, this part of the definition can be easily understood as being at a place where they don’t feel comfortable because they are under another individual's influence.

The second part allows for broad interpretations—“through the means of force, fraud, or coercion”—includes three general situations. Force covers cases in which physical restraint or harm is used as well as confinement in order to control victims. Fraud includes the use of trickery or bribery in defining the crime. Promising someone a better life, a job, or money but then switching up the agreement and not following through would count as fraud and fall under the second element. The last part to the second element, coercion, covers physical or psychological effects on the victim that may involve the use of violence, threats, lies, or debt bondage.

The third element—“with the intent of obtaining commercial sex or to exploit the individual for labor or services”—means being under the ownership or control of someone where a person is forced to work for another. It also covers any sex act on account of anything of value given to or received by any person. These three elements are essential to proving an individual is guilty of human trafficking (“Officing in Trafficking in Persons”).

iii. Enforcement of Laws Associated with Human Trafficking

Laws reflect the norms a state or country would like to have their people follow and create a concrete set of rules that everyone can agree and abide by. The rules on human

trafficking among many countries internationally have the same foundation and strive to achieve the same goals: reducing rates of human trafficking. Although these laws are set in place by the government, it's up to the criminal justice to enforce and make sure people obey them ("Criminal Justice Jobs"). The criminal justice system includes the court, police officers, and the correctional system. Not every country has a reliable and unprejudiced criminal justice system. Stories of Vietnam's corrupt government are heard of constantly on the news and through word of mouth to this day, where locals are angered by how unfairly they are treated on the road while running errands. The United States does not lack stories where a police officer may be treating someone unfairly, but this doesn't compare to how often locals are able to bribe their way out of crimes in Vietnam. This leaves the question of how severe a crime must be such that officials are not bribed, and what does this mean for human trafficking cases? How do corruption and bribery in the enforcement systems in the United States and Vietnam affect human trafficking outcomes?

The prosecution section of the *2022 Trafficking in Peoples Report in Vietnam* stated that there were 67 prosecution cases that were not reported with information specific enough to be determined whether it fits the international definition of human trafficking. In order to accurately measure how a country is doing while combating this crisis, it is beneficial for a country to take this seriously and make reports that accurately represent its data. When coming together as a world, each can do its part through its inputs and efforts in combating this disaster. With the higher legal authorities being this loose about the situation, it's anticipated that local police officers wouldn't feel the obligation of thoroughly investigating and helping its people during even bigger cases.

Locals in Vietnam have plentiful stories of bribing themselves out of road trouble. Antonia Gabric, for example, is a traveler who currently lives in Vietnam while documenting his experiences and stories of occurrences. Gabric once wrote about the corruption of Vietnamese polices stating that if ever pulled over, to simply bribe them with money. He had also linked a video from Charlie Pryor. Pryor documented his experience while with his wife's family in Vietnam of getting pulled over in Vietnam and how the police's motive really was to try to get as much money from him as possible. After taking too long to get the money, they threatened to increase the price. Once becoming aware they were being recorded, they finally dealt with the solution through legal means, like writing a ticket (Gabric). Seeing how these Vietnamese police officers only cared about how much money they get, raises concerns about how more severe crimes are dealt with. Citizens rely on their local police to report their legal problems, but if their main motive is personal monetary gain, then how trustworthy can these officers really be? Knowing how unreliable they are, this can discourage people from reporting their trafficking cases and finding help from legal authorities as they're afraid they won't have enough money to bribe for help.

Although America seems like a place of luxury and perfection to many foreigners who long to live in America, it too, does have some corruption. When compared to Vietnam, we don't usually hear as many stories of bad experiences with cops, but the Cato Institute's National Police Misconduct Reporting Project was able to track down that 1% of police commit

misconduct on duty, most of the time, to get a confession (“Police Misconduct”). The story of officer Jon Burge was shared in this source of how he put a plastic bag over someone’s head until they lost consciousness because he was trying to obtain a confession which resulted in him getting fired and convicted.

Vietnam and America are both places filled with cops that have different personalities and qualities. Nonetheless, this doesn’t ensure that everybody who is at risk of trafficking has a legal system and authorities, where they could rely on when put into trafficking situations. Despite how descriptive and well-defined human-trafficking laws are, it is up to how authorities enforce their laws and use their position to do what their people need them to do.

iv: Role of Geography in Human Trafficking

Fig 1: Map Of Vietnam (*Vietnam-Map-Features-Locator.Jpg 1,600×1,326 Pixels, Britannica*)

Vietnam is an "S-shaped" nation that shares a border with China to the North, Laos and Cambodia to the West, the South China Sea to the East. The majority of Vietnam's northern geography is mountainous. Certain highland sections are covered in a thick layer of rainforest, and the region's lowlands are home to densely populated and intensively grown rice farms. The nation’s humid tropical monsoon climate is significantly influenced by the East Sea. The recurrent monsoons that cause periodic flooding results in home, infrastructure, and crop destruction and water contamination (“Monsoon Season”). Given that Vietnam is a relatively small country, all these natural disasters and its topography result in a lack of productivity in economics. Crops become destroyed and farmers fall deeper into debt, not making enough for profit. People who fall into poverty are more easily bribed and may fall victim to trafficking. They might feel the need to find better work by migrating somewhere, making them more

vulnerable to traffickers. People even sell their own family members, including their children, to survive or in the hopes their loved ones might get a chance at a better life (Wright, 2015).

In contrast to natural disasters in Vietnam, such as monsoons that affects about 400,000 people, which is about 0.4% of the Vietnamese population, the same disasters affect about 0.1% of the population in America. Additionally, the U.S. is supported by a significant number of natural resources, including a vast landmass, long coasts, fresh water, oil, and coal, and a diversified population. It is less likely for people in America to experience poverty given that 18% of the land is arable, where plantations are growing, and where there is a plentiful supply of fuel for industrial machinery and technology.

Geographical factors also affect transit nations. Due to how simple and convenient transportation is, transit countries serve as connecting routes between origin and destination countries for human trafficking organizations (“Trafficking Routes,” 2019). Traffickers can move people from origin countries, which tend to be poorer nations or third world nations, to transit countries with weak borders such as Turkey or Morocco. Destination countries, such as America or Thailand, are frequently larger nations where the demands on the services of trafficking victims are higher. This is due to the fact that the destination countries are often wealthier and have more money to pay for illegal labor (“Trafficking Routes,” 2019). Vietnam is a great example of an origin country because of how poorly developed it is, making it easier for traffickers to exploit victims' lack of education as well as lack of awareness regarding the social, political, and ultimately legal repercussions in the nation. Due to the ease with which law enforcement may be bought off and the popularity of neighboring countries like Cambodia and China as major hubs for sex, labor, and human trafficking, Vietnam's borders are frequently crossed.

v. Social Economics Affecting Human Trafficking

About 332 million people live in the United States while 97.5 million people live in Vietnam. America is 30 times larger than Vietnam by landmass, showing how densely populated Vietnam is. The densely packed country results in high poverty rates, as limited resources are stripped away from those who aren't able to afford the food, clean water, and those resources that allow a decent life. The people of the country reflect how prosperous the country is, so poverty rates are a main factor to this since it shows how available jobs and opportunities are to the people (“Explaining Poverty”). In Vietnam, “around one in five Vietnamese usually live below the economic security line of \$5.50 USD a day”, and 4.4% of the population are living in poverty (Le, 2022). Researchers have also found that trafficking in young people who receive youth housing services has reported experiencing human trafficking in some way (Mostajabian et al., 2019). This shows how poverty and homelessness is a significant factor to how young people could be affected by trafficking. The main root of poverty is lack of education, so influencing and supporting youth through their schooling could lessen the chances of poverty and even possibly lessen the risk of more people being trafficked.

In the U.S., it is mandatory for children to go to school however, children can be seen roaming the streets of Vietnam at any time of day instead of being in school. Vietnam laws have many loopholes, where employers still hire children between the ages of 5-17 (“Child Labour”). Needy families allow their kids to go work so they’d get through another day with enough money. It may seem abnormal to see a kid roaming the street at 12:00 PM on a Tuesday, but with how normal it is for kids to work starting at ages as young as five, pedestrians live with this as a normality. Many would feel pity for how hard they have to work at such a young age, but little gets done about this situation and people continue to move on with their lives giving little attention to the problem. Wandering the streets alone without parents to try to sell something and make money makes the kids so much more vulnerable to human trafficking. This makes a strong point of why children around the age of twelve become victims of trafficking and why school being a safe place of shelter and knowledge is so important. Education is important to inform children about the dangers of the world like human trafficking but also allow students to grow up with jobs that give them an income to support their needs. Well-educated kids that escape poverty are less likely to fall into situations of trafficking because they wouldn’t need to go to measures where they have to travel away from home to make money or be a victim of job or investment fraud (Gardner, 2023).

Not everyone can easily access education and equal opportunity in Vietnam. Students from lower class families might not get treated equally in schools. In Vietnam's rural areas, many students still attend school under very challenging circumstances. Schools are frequently outdated, poorly stated, and improperly maintained. In addition to being generally poorly lighted, the classrooms can be drafty, freezing in the winter, and hot in the spring and summer (“Rural Vietnam”). “Educational completion is much lower for children in the poorest households than the richest ones. By age 19, only a fifth of students from the poorest 20 percent remain in school, compared with 80 percent of those in the wealthiest 20 percent,” (Tran et al., 2022). These children who have to learn in hardship usually end up pursuing employment as farmers, fishers, miners, or any domestic work, which doesn’t require much schooling but is also typically the main target for trafficking.

vi. Societal Impacts on the Outlook of Human Trafficking

The community in which people are surrounded is very important on how they view things and their outlook on certain topics, one being human trafficking. The town or country people are in casts news that is relevant to the people there but it can also leave out important subjects that should be known. This affects how aware people are and also limits people’s knowledge of the risk they might be in just because they don’t know. Many people in Vietnam are not exposed to the information of human trafficking because of the censorship in Vietnam. The government censors topics that test the legitimacy, corruption, and human rights issues (World Report, 2019). This could be the result of how the community handles the topic.

In Vietnam, criticizing or challenging a rule through social media or even peaceful protests, are prohibited (World Report, 2019). This limits what information is disseminated

across the country. As social media is controlled by the government, the posts that people make in that country minorly criticizing how the government may be dealing with something could get them in big trouble including harsh imprisonment sentences. This would intimidate the people posting as anything could get them thrown in prison if the government disagrees with it (World Report, 2019). So, suggesting and protesting the awareness of human trafficking can be very intimidating for someone who lives in Vietnam. With everyone just neglecting the severity of this catastrophe, it could easily be forgotten and awareness could decrease among the civilians raising danger for everyone.

vii. Conclusion

Seeing how laws between countries are so similar when it comes to human trafficking since it follows an international definition, Vietnam still lacks awareness and enforcement. This is a big red flag as to why Vietnam is doing poorer compared to the United States. The geography that the country is located in, which is uncontrollable, also contributes to high rates of human trafficking. Vietnam became a major transit country of human trafficking because of its geographical location. The natural disasters have also affected its people causing them to live life in poverty or lack of education leaving them to be extremely vulnerable to trafficking.

After carefully examining and contrasting the two countries, the research has discovered that the legal frameworks in Vietnam are far less developed than in the U.S.; it is far more challenging to gather reliable information about the most efficient means of reducing human trafficking. The Vietnamese government's ban on protest and empowerment further explains why the problem of human trafficking is not widely recognized as being serious enough. However, human trafficking is a major issue in America and for the whole world itself even if one country may be combatting it more efficiently.

From these factors, Vietnam's government can do more to benefit its people in order for trafficking rates to be reduced. This can include providing money to schools and organizations that help people who cannot easily access those. Having a better law enforcement system is something that would be beneficial as well. Putting money and time into disciplining officers and being more strict towards those in the criminal justice system is needed to make sure that people are guilty of the right cause and incriminated fairly. To combat the problem of natural disasters, the outcome of it is something that is uncontrollable; how they decide to use their money to restore the land and the people's well-being to help out their lives will chain back to putting them at less risk of human trafficking dangers. People's desire of having a better quality life is what brings them to being trafficked most of the time so if Vietnam puts effort into helping their people survive, then this will reduce the risk of exploitation. Nonetheless, trafficking occurs all over the world and it's unpredictable when and where the next case might happen. No matter what, it's still important to take precautions and prevent as many outcomes as possible to save the lives of victims around the world.

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